

Synthesis of Potential Antiradiation Agents. Part II. Some 1,3-Thiazane Derivatives*

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Several 1,3-thiazano derivatives have been synthesised as potential antiradiation agents. Crotonic acid and itaconic acid as well as methyl methacrylate on treatment with ammonium dithiocarbamate provide the open-chain intermediates which on acid cyclisation result in the corresponding 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazanes. Independent syntheses of these products have been made and the spectrophotometric evidence in support of their structures has been discussed.

In earlier communications^{1,2}, the synthesis of a number of thiazolidine and rhodanine derivatives as potential radioprotective agents has been discussed. Following the report by Campaigne *et al.*³ that 3-(β -aminoethyl)-1,3-thiazane-2,4-dione hydrochloride is an active radioprotective agent, we have synthesised some 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane derivatives (II, IV and V) for evaluation as radioprotective agents.

Crotonic acid on treatment with ammonium dithiocarbamate provided a mixture of two compounds which were separated by fractional crystallisation as a yellow and a white product. Analysis of the two compounds agreed with $C_5H_7ONS_2$ and $C_5H_9O_2NS_2$, respectively. The white product could be converted into the yellow product on treatment with 25% H_2SO_4 .

The white product $C_5H_9O_2NS_2$, dissolved readily in bicarbonate solution with effervescence and showed the characteristic absorptions for a carboxylic acid grouping near 1700 cm^{-1} in the IR region. The product also showed absorption at 1625 cm^{-1} , typical of $-NH_2$ deformation of primary amide, and 1031 cm^{-1} for $C=S$. This open-chain compound has obviously resulted by the addition of the dithiocarbamyl ion at the positively polarised β -carbon of the unsaturated acid. For structural confirmation, β -dithiocarbamylbutyric acid (I) has also been synthesised by treatment of β -brombutyric acid⁴ with ammonium dithiocarbamate at pH 3—3.5.

The yellow cyclised product, $C_5H_7ONS_2$, showed the characteristic IR absorption at 1605 cm^{-1} ($C=O$) and 1488 cm^{-1} (thioureide). It also showed absorption at $300\text{ m}\mu$ and $250\text{ m}\mu$ in the UV region, similar to that shown by 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane, prepared by us according to Jansen and Mathes' procedure⁵ as well as that reported in the literature for similar compounds⁶.

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1. Choughuley and Chadha, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 437.
2. Mamdapur *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1965, 42, 825.
3. Campaigne *et al.*, Abst. papers 141st meeting. Am. Chem. Soc., Washington D.C., March 1962, p.32N.
4. Grimshaw *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 68.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2860.
6. Potter, Ph.D. Dissertation, Duke University, Durham, North Carolina, U.S.A., 1962; Brown, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 61, 463.

The reaction of methyl methacrylate with ammonium dithiocarbamate was studied likewise. The intermediate product was obtained as an oily mass, which in efforts to purify it cyclised to the corresponding thiazane derivative. The intermediate ester was, however, characterized by its acid hydrolysis to β -dithiocarbamylisobutyric acid (III). The same acid was also obtained by treatment of methyl β -bromoisobutyrate⁷ with ammonium dithiocarbamate, followed by acid hydrolysis of the resulting ester. Both the intermediate ester and the corresponding acid on treatment, with mineral acid furnished 5-methyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane (IV). The UV spectrum of (IV) was characteristic⁶ of a 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane derivative. The IR spectra of (III) and (IV) showed the requisite absorption bands.

Itaconic acid on treatment with ammonium dithiocarbamate afforded a colorless crystalline intermediate which on acid cyclisation provided a yellow product. This showed characteristic UV absorption at 309.5 m μ and 259 m μ as well as IR absorption for 4-keto, carboxyl, and thioureide groups and has been assigned the structure 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane-5-acetic acid. Ethyl ester of this acid could be easily prepared in ethanolic hydrogen chloride. This ester was also prepared independently by treating diethyl bromomethylsuccinate with ammonium dithiocarbamate. The intermediate open-chain di-ester could not be isolated as it showed the tendency to cyclise instantaneously. The cyclized ester on acid hydrolysis provided 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane-5-acetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

IR spectra were taken as KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer infracord Spectrophotometer, Model 137B. UV spectra were recorded on a Carl Zeiss Recording Spectrophotometer RPQ 20A.

β -Dithiocarbamylbutyric Acid (I)

(a). *From Crotonic Acid*.—Ammonium dithiocarbamate⁸ (0.12M, 13.2 g.) was added to a solution of crotonic acid (0.1M, 8.6 g.) in water (40 ml) in small portions in the cold

*All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

7. Price and Coyner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1906.

8. Redemann *et al.*, "Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. III, p. 764, 1955, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., N.Y.

with intermittent shaking. The reaction mixture was kept at 10-12° for 3 days. On concentration, a yellowish white solid (8.2 g.) separated. On fractional crystallisation, a white solid was obtained which was recrystallised from water in white rhombic crystals, m.p. 152-54°. (Found: C, 33.36; H, 5.20; N, 7.80. $C_5H_9O_4NS_2$ requires C, 33.52; H, 5.02; N, 7.82%). IR absorption: 3335, 3280, 3175 (OH, NH_2), 1695, (-COOH), 1628 (NH_2 of amide), 1031 (C=S), and 3,000-2500 cm^{-1} (small bands, typical for COOH).

(b). *From β -Bromobutyric Acid.*—To β -bromobutyric acid (1.8 g.) in aqueous ethanol (10 ml) ammonium dithiocarbamate (1.5g.) was added and the reaction mixture kept at 10-12° at pH 3.5 for 3 days. A product, m.p. 152-54°, identical to the one obtained in (a), resulted.

6-Methyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane (II)

A suspension of the acid (I) (2g.) in 25% H_2SO_4 (10 ml) was heated at 80° for 1 hr. with mechanical stirring. Crushed ice (10 g.) was added to the resulting mixture when a yellow solid separated (0.8 g.). This was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 134-35°. (Found: C, 37.47; H, 4.50; N, 8.74. $C_5H_9ONS_2$ requires C, 37.28; H, 4.35; N, 8.69%). IR absorption: 3175, 3125 (NH), 1695 (4-CO). 1471 (thioureide), and 1050 cm^{-1} (C=S). UV absorption: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 404 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 115); 310 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 14,370), and 259 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 13,150).

β -Dithiocarbamylisobutyric Acid (III)

(a). *From Methyl Methacrylate.*—After keeping a mixture of methyl methacrylate (0.1 M, 9.8g.) in ethanol (40 ml) and ammonium dithiocarbamate (1.12M, 13.5g.) in water (15 ml) at 10-12° for 3 days, an intermediate oily ester was obtained (11.2g.) This product (2 g.), when heated to reflux with 5% H_2SO_4 (30 ml) in ethanol (15 ml) for 15 hr., afforded a water-soluble acid and a benzene-soluble yellow product. The water-soluble product on concentration and cooling furnished a white solid (0.7 g.) which on repeated crystallisation from water provided colorless plates, m.p. 136-37°. (Found: C, 33.22; H, 5.30; N, 7.75. $C_5H_9O_4NS_2$ requires C, 33.52; H, 5.02; N, 7.62%). IR absorption; 3360, 3270, 3175 (OH, NH_2), 1695 (-COOH), 1613 (NH_2 of amide), 1085 (C=S), and 3000-2500 cm^{-1} (small bands, typical of COOH).

The yellow benzene-soluble product on concentration and cooling furnished yellow needles, m.p. 115-16° and identified as 5-methyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane, being identical with (IV), obtained by acid cyclisation of (III) (*vide infra*).

(b). *From Methyl β -Bromoisobutyrate.*—To methyl β -bromoisobutyrate (2g.) in ethanol (10 ml) ammonium dithiocarbamate (2 g.) in water (5 ml.) was added and the reaction mixture kept at 10-12° for 3 days. The resulting ester on acid hydrolysis provided a carboxylic acid, indistinguishable from (III), as prepared above (m.p., mixed m.p., and IR).

5-Methyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane (IV)

The open-chain ester, prepared in (a) above or the corresponding acid (III), on cyclisation with 50% H_2SO_4 , using the same procedure as for (II), afforded an oily product which solidified under vacuum. On crystallisation from dilute ethanol yellow fluffy needles, m.p. 115-16°, were obtained. (Found: C, 37.37; H, 4.30; N, 8.49. $C_5H_9ONS_2$ requires

C, 37.28; H, 4.35; N, 8.68%). IR absorption: 3205, 3125 (-NH); 1706 (4-CO), 1471 (thioureide), and 1058 cm^{-1} (C=S). UV absorption: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 403 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 130); 309.5 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 14,940) 259 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 13,810).

2-Thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane-5-acetic Acid (V)

(a). *From Itaconic Acid*.—A solution of ammonium dithiocarbamate (0.1 M , 11 g.) in water (25 ml) was added to a solution of itaconic acid (0.08 M , 10.4 g.) in ethanol (135 ml) and the mixture kept at 10-12° for 8 days when a white crystalline solid (13.1 g.) was obtained. This on acid cyclisation with 50% H_2SO_4 afforded yellow a solid (2 g.). The filtrate on concentration provided an additional amount (7.5 g.) of the same product. On repeated crystallisation from dilute ethanol, clusters of needles, m.p. 189-90° (decomp), were obtained. (Found: C, 35.32; H, 3.36; N, 6.83. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_2\text{NS}_2$ requires C, 35.12, H, 3.40; N, 6.82%). IR absorption: 3175, 3125 (NH), 1709 (4-CO), 1075 (COOH), 1481 (thioureide), and 1070 cm^{-1} (C=S). UV absorption: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 405 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 120); 200.5 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 11,780), and 259 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 10,760).

(b). *Form Diethyl Bromomethylsuccinate*.—Diethyl bromomethylsuccinate (2.7 g.), prepared from diethyl itaconate and hydrogen bromide, following the procedure employed for the preparation of methyl β -bromoisobutyrate⁷, was taken in ethanol (10 ml) and treated with ammonium dithiocarbamate (2 g.) in water (10 ml) and the mixture kept at 10-12° for 3 days. The resulting oily product exhibited superimposable IR spectrum with the ethyl ester of (V). This ester on acid hydrolysis provided a yellow product which on crystallisation from dilute ethanol furnished a product indistinguishable from (V) (m.p., mixed m.p., and IR).

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